

Singlet Fission in Pyrene-Fused Azaacene Dimers

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Abstract: Singlet fission has emerged as a promising strategy to avoid the loss of extra energy through thermalization in solar cells. Herein, we report a family of dimers constituted by nitrogen-doped pyrene-fused acenes that undergo singlet fission with TQY as high as 125%, which provide new perspectives for nitrogenated polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and for the design of new materials for singlet fission.

Singlet fission (SF) has emerged as a promising strategy to overcome the Shockley-Queisser limit that predicts a maximum power conversion efficiency of 33.7 % for a single junction device.^[1] This is because, in SF, a singlet excited state (S_1) splits into two triplet excited states (T_1) and hence the generation of the extra exciton per absorbed photon avoids the loss of extra energy through thermalization. SF had been observed in several families of conjugated molecules and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons,^[2] among which the acene family have shown a prominent position. For instance, acene dimers have become key to understand how structural and electronic factors influence the dynamics of the formation and decay of triplet excitons.^[3] Since singlet SF efficiencies are known to increase with the number of linearly-fused rings and pentacene is the most stable of the higher acenes, the synthesis and study of pentacene dimers have received a lot of attention,^[2a, 2b] among which maximum triplet quantum yield values (TQY) of 200% have been reported.

Yet the triplet energy of pentacene is not well-matched for use in solar cells,^[4] and also, the stability of pentacene derivatives is limited in comparison to the shorter acenes.^[5] On this regard, tetracene has been investigated as an alternative since it shows triplet energies above the bandgap of silicon^[4a, 4b] and is known to be more stable than pentacene.^[5] In addition, dimers constituted by

tetracene have been recently reported with TQY $\geq 100\%$.^[6]

Substitutional nitrogen-doping is another potential approach to improve the properties of acenes for SF, since the resulting azaacenes are more stable than the corresponding acenes and also their energy levels that can be tuned with the number and the position of the nitrogen atoms.^[7] Nevertheless, azaacenes remain practically unexplored in SF and only a few studies about monomeric azaacenes in thin films have been reported.^[8]

Herein, we report a family of dimers constituted by nitrogen-doped pyrene-fused acenes that undergo SF (Figure 1). This series of regioisomeric dimers are constituted by two dibenzodiazahexacene cores bridged by a phenylene bridge in an ortho-, meta- or para- substitution pattern (**o-DAD**, **m-DAD** and **p-DAD**), which show the electronic structure of two diazatetracenes (highlighted in pink) as the result of the localization of sextets in the off-linear pyrene rings (highlighted in sky blue) that compartmentalize the acene backbone in smaller and more stable tetracenic residues. The combination of ultrafast transient absorption measurements with global and target analyses reveal TQY as high as 125% and a detailed SF mechanistic insight for pyrene-fused azaacenes, which altogether provide new perspectives not only for azaacenes and nitrogenated pyrene-fused acenes, but also for the design of new materials with enhanced properties for SF.

Dibenzodiazahexacene dimers **o-DAD**, **m-DAD** and **p-DAD** are members of the pyrene-fused azaacene^[9] family that combine linear annulations (acene backbone) with periodic off-linear bisannulations

Figure 1. Chemical structures of **o-DAD**, **m-DAD** and **p-DAD**.

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(pyrene residues). Pyrene-fused azaacenes have shown a high stability as illustrated by synthesis of monodisperse nanoribbons with up to 30 linearly-fused rings^[10] and of polydisperse nanoribbons with ~80 linearly-fused rings.^[11] We selected dibenzodiaza-hexacene derivatives with TIPS-acetylene substituents because of their tetracene electronic structure, their stability and solubility.^[12] **o-DAD**, **m-DAD** and **p-DAD** were synthesized following the route set out on Scheme 1. A key intermediate is the synthesis of pyrene dione **A** that will enable the synthesis of the dibenzodiaza-hexacene core and also the coupling with other units. This structure is quite challenging as it is a completely asymmetric pyrene derivative. To obtain this intermediate, we developed a new synthetic route with pyrene as the starting point that combines desymmetrisation across the 2 and 7 positions and across the K-regions. The first step is the introduction of a *tert*-butyl group in position 2 of pyrene by Friedel-Crafts alkylation.^[13] Then, 2-*tert*-butylpyrene **B** was borylated on the 7 position through an iridium-catalysed reaction (63%). Subsequently, we carried out the oxidation of one of the K-regions of pyrene **C** using NaIO₄ and RuCl₃ as a catalyst, which to our surprise work very well (53%), highlighting the broad functional group compatibility of this reaction. Also the cyclocondensation of dione **A** and anthracenediamine **D**^[7c] was satisfactory (56%), yielding the asymmetric dibenzodiaza-hexacene **E** with a boronate ester that can be further engaged in cross-coupling reactions. Suzuki cross coupling reactions between **E** and diiodobenzene with conventional heating led to poor yields <7%. Conversely, when the reactions were carried out with microwave heating higher yields were obtained in shorter reaction times. The **o-DAD**, **m-DAD** and **p-DAD** dimers were obtained via microwave-assisted Suzuki cross-coupling reaction between the precursor **E** with *ortho*-, *meta* and *para*-diiodobenzene affording respectively the desired *ortho*-, *meta* and *para* compounds (25 %, 45 % and 23 % for **o-DAD**, **m-DAD** and **p-DAD**, respectively). For reference purposes dibenzodiaza-hexacene (**DAM**) monomer was prepared by condensation of 2,7-di-*tert*-butyl pyrene-4,5-dione^[13] and anthracenediamine **D**.^[7c] Complete synthetic procedures including ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time of flight high-resolution mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF HRMS) and a X-ray crystal structure for **DAM** are provided in the supporting information.

To shed light onto electronic interactions between the two dibenzodiaza-hexacenes in the different dimers, we first turned to steady-state investigations in solvents with different polarity, namely toluene, THF and benzonitrile (Figures 2a and S1; Table S1). Similar absorption spectra were recorded for **DAM**, **o-DAD**, **m-DAD**, and **p-DAD** with a series of maxima in the 300-425 and the 450-700 nm ranges (Figure 2a). A closer look at the 588 and 640 nm maxima reveals that, on one hand, **o-DAD**, **m-DAD**, and **p-DAD** are red-shifted in comparison to **DAM**. The 478, 506, and 540 nm maxima, on the other hand, are blue-shifted in **m-DAD**, and **p-DAD** and red-shifted on **o-DAD**. The extinction coefficients of **o-DAD**, **m-DAD**, and **p-DAD** are not doubled in comparison to that of the reference **DAM**. This speaks for electronic interactions in the ground state as seen for pentacene dimers.^[14] The computed TD-DFT spectra at B3LYP-6-311+g(2d,p)/PBEh-3c level (Figure S2) and at the M06-2X-toluene-6-311+g(2d,p)/PBEh-3c level (Figure S3) show the same trends as the experimental spectra. In both cases, the first absorption peak position is essentially the same for all dimers, and appears at slightly lower energies than **DAM**, meanwhile, the second transition appears redshifted for **o-DAD**, in agreement with the experimental spectra.

Scheme 1. a) Synthesis of dimers (**o-DAD**, **m-DAD** and **p-DAD**). b) Synthesis of reference monomer (**DAM**).

In the electronic excited state (Figures 2b and S4; Table S1), the interactions are even more evident and more dependent on the solvent polarity. **DAM** fluoresces in the red to NIR range with quantum yields of 25%, 22%, and 16% in toluene, THF, and benzonitrile, respectively. The vibrational fine structure as seen in toluene (Figure 2b) gradually disappears when inspecting THF and benzonitrile (Figure S4). **o-DAD**, **m-DAD**, and **p-DAD** all fluoresce, but with much lower quantum yields than **DAM**: 13%, 20%, and 19%, respectively, in toluene (Figure 2b). At this point, we relate the fluorescence quenching to the interactions between the two dibenzodiaza-hexacenes, which intensifies from **o-DAD** to **p-DAD** and **m-DAD**. In time correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) measurements with **DAM** only a single, moderately long-lived component of 26.0 ns was found in toluene. Interestingly, **o-DAD** and **p-DAD** revealed three components rather than one, that is, contributions from a short-, an intermediate-, and a long-lived species.^[15] What was 26.0 ns in **DAM**, is 1.7 and 15.9 ns for **o-DAD** and **p-DAD** as the short-lived species, and 21.8 ns for **m-DAD** as the intermediate-lived species, respectively, in toluene. In benzonitrile, the lifetimes were as short as 1.0 ns in, for example, **o-DAD** (Figures S5-S8 and Table S2).^[16]

The electrochemical properties of **DAM**, **o-DAD**, **m-DAD** and **p-DAD** were studied by cyclic voltammetry in an Ar-saturated solution of CH₂Cl₂ with *n*Bu₄NPF₆ as electrolyte (Figure 2c). The oxidation and reduction potentials are given *versus* the ferrocene/ferrocenium (Fc/Fc⁺) couple that was used as an internal standard. The voltammograms of all dimers and the reference monomer show two

reduction waves and one oxidation wave with no remarkable differences in the half-wave potentials (Table S3).

Figure 2. a) Absorption and b) fluorescence (photoexcitation at 550 nm with an optical density of 0.025) spectra of **DAM**, **o-DAD**, **m-DAD** and **p-DAD** in Toluene. c) Cyclic voltammograms of **DAM**, **o-DAD**, **m-DAD** and **p-DAD** in an Ar-saturated 0.1 M solution of $n\text{Bu}_4\text{NPF}_6$ in CH_2Cl_2 .

The energy levels were estimated from the electronic absorption and electrochemical measurements (Tables S1 and S3), which correlate well with the DFT calculations (Table S4). The optical HOMO-LUMO gaps ($E_{\text{gap}}^{\text{opt}} \sim 1.8 \text{ eV}$) and electrochemical HOMO-LUMO gaps ($E_{\text{gap}}^{\text{CV}} \sim 1.8 \text{ eV}$) are nearly identical for **DAM**, **o-DAD**, **m-DAD**, and **p-DAD**. The electrochemical LUMO levels (or electron affinities) and the electrochemical HOMO levels (or ionisation potentials), which were estimated from the onset of the first reduction and the oxidation potential respectively, are also nearly identical for **DAM**, **o-DAD**, **m-DAD**, and **p-DAD** ($E_{\text{LUMO}} \sim -3.6 \text{ eV}$ and $E_{\text{HOMO}} \sim -5.4 \text{ eV}$). Electronic structure calculations yielded very similar relative results with subtle differences for the four studied molecules (Table S4). The computed $2T_1$ is similar to S_1 for B3LYP in vacuum and remarkably similar for the M06-2X Hamiltonian computed in toluene (Table S5) for all dimers, which therefore fulfil the energetic requirements for SF.

Femtosecond (fs-TAS) and nanosecond transient absorption (ns-TAS) measurements were performed to gather a more detailed understanding of the excited state dynamics. Fitting the differential absorption data with a combination of multiwavelength and target analyses sheds light onto lifetimes, quantum yields, and species associated spectra (SAS). In the case of **DAM** (Figure S9-S12), 505 nm excitation experiments are best fit by a kinetic model that is based on the sequential formation of three species, namely (S_1), (S_1)_{SOL}, and (T_1) (Figure S13 and Table S6). TQYs are of 12% and 8% for **DAM** in toluene and benzonitrile were respectively obtained.^[17] To establish the triplet excited state features, we turned to triplet-triplet energy-transfer experiments using *N*-methylfulleropyrrolidine (**N-MFP**, $8.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$) as a triplet sensitizer using 480 nm (800 nJ) photoexcitation (Figure S14-S17).

Fitting the fs-TAS and ns-TAS data of **m-DAD** (Figure S18-S21) required the use of a four species kinetic model (Figure S22 and Table S7). After excitation at 505 nm, the singlet excited (S_1S_0) state undergoes solvent reorganization to afford (S_1S_0)_{SOL} that transforms

quickly and directly into a correlated triplet excited ($^1(T_1T_1)$) state. The last step in the sequence is spin decoherence that results in the uncorrelated triplet excited ((T_1+T_1)) state (Figure S22 and Table S7). TQYs for $^1(T_1T_1)$ and (T_1+T_1) are 70% and 27% in toluene and 30% and 32% in benzonitrile, respectively.

Fitting the fs-TAS / ns-TAS data for **o-DAD** (Figure 3a, 3b, and S23-S26 and Table S8) and **p-DAD** (Figure S27-S30 and Table S9) necessitated the modifications of the deactivation mechanism. In this case, (S_1S_0)_{CT}, which is a virtual intermediate in **m-DAD**, becomes a real intermediate in **o-DAD** and **p-DAD**. In turn, a five species kinetic model is applied (Figure 3c). The deconvoluted fs- and ns-TAS spectra derived from target analysis are illustrated as a leading example for **o-DAD** (Figure 3a, 3b, and S23-S26). 505 nm excitation leads to the instantaneous formation of (S_1S_0) followed by solvent reorganization. The correspondingly formed (S_1S_0)_{SOL} transitions in a parallel fashion to $^1(T_1T_1)$; a fast and direct pathway, on one hand, as well as a slow and indirect pathway. Implicit in the indirect pathway is (S_1S_0)_{CT} as a real intermediate *en-route* towards $^1(T_1T_1)$; this is the extra species relative to the kinetic model used for **m-DAD**.^{[18][14a]} $^1(T_1T_1)$ TQYs in toluene of 125% and 82% for **o-DAD** and **p-DAD**, respectively, corroborate SF in the deactivation of them. Increasing the polarity leads along with shorter lifetimes to lower TQYs of 92% for **o-DAD** and 35% for **p-DAD**. The immediate outcome of using benzonitrile is an energetic lowering of the real intermediate (S_1S_0)_{CT}. As a matter of fact, we note that this pathway intensifies from 50% in toluene to 70% in benzonitrile. In addition, the equilibrium between (S_1S_0)_{CT} and $^1(T_1T_1)$ is heavily shifted towards the former rather than the latter and, in turn, the direct deactivation is favoured. TQYs of ($T_1 + T_1$) remain in all cases at around 30%.

A likely rationale for higher $^1(T_1T_1)$ TQYs in **o-DAD** and **p-DAD** is the directing nature of ortho- and para-substitution and, as such, the better electronic communication between tetracenes. Stronger coupling must be also responsible for the fact that the intermediate (S_1S_0)_{CT} state is only observable in **o-DAD** and **p-DAD**, while it is a virtual state in **m-DAD**. Finally, the close spatial proximity between the two dibenzozahexacenes in **o-DAD** results in an increase of electronic communication and enables the highest TQYs. The latter is supported by the experimental and calculated (M06-2X-toluene-6-311+g(2d,p)/PBEh-3c) electronic absorption spectra (Figures 2a, S2 and S3) that illustrate how the direct contact between tetracene units in **o-DAD** has a strong effect on the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition, which combines contributions with a sizable Charge Transfer (CT) character due to the transfer of charge between the two different aromatic tetracene moieties (Figures S31-S33). While in the case of **m-DAD** and **p-DAD** the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition is not redshifted because the two tetracene units are spatially decoupled (Figures 2a, S31 and S32). This direct contact is also reflected experimentally by the higher fluorescence quenching on **o-DAD** (Figure 2b). In order to check the DFT findings, we also computed the excited states of the **o-DAD-H** model system (this is an **o-DAD** model in which the TIPS groups have been exchanged by H) at the NEVPT2(8,8)/def-SV(P) level. This yielded two Local Excitation (LE) states at 2.28 and 2.39 eV and two darker CT states at 2.36 and 2.37 eV, which confirms the M06-2X finding yet also suggesting that these CT states might be nearly degenerate to the LE S_1 states. Also, at this theory level, the T_1 state appears at 1.23 eV, which is also roughly at half the S_1 energy.

Figure 3. a) Deconvoluted fs-TA spectra of the singlet excited (S_1S_0) (black), and the stabilized singlet excited state (S_1S_0)_{SOL} (red) of **o-DAD** as obtained by target analysis in toluene. b) Deconvoluted ns-TA spectra of the stabilized singlet excited state (S_1S_0)_{SOL} (black), the intermediate CT-state (S_1S_0)_{CT} (red), the singlet correlated triplet state $^1(T_1T_1)$ (blue), and the uncorrelated triplet excited state (T_1+T_1) (green) of **o-DAD** as obtained by target analysis in toluene. c) Kinetic model used to fit the transient absorption data for **o-DAD** and **p-DAD**.

In conclusion, we have reported the synthesis of a new family of regioisomeric diazatetracene dimers constituted of two dibenzodiazahexacene units linked by a phenylene ring in an ortho-, metha- and para- substitution pattern. In **o-DAD** the two tetracene units are in close contact, while in the case of **m-DAD** and **p-DAD** the two tetracene units are spatially decoupled, as demonstrated by a combination of electronic absorption and photoluminescence measurements and theoretical calculations. Femtosecond (fs-TAS) and nanosecond transient absorption (ns-TAS) measurements reveal how the enhanced electronic communication in **o-DAD** gives rise to a TQY >100%. Overall this work provides new application perspectives for pyrene-fused azaacenes, but also for the design of new materials with enhanced properties for SF, in which the triplet energy and the stability are better suited for use in solar cells.

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- [15] For **m-DAD** the short-lived component is invisible.
- [16] What changes in addition is the ratio between short-, intermediate-, and long-lived component in favour of the intermediate-lived one.
- [17] It should be mentioned that the lifetime of $(S_1)_{SOL}$ is shorter in the more polar solvents than in the more apolar solvents.
- [18] A direct consequence of the parallel pathway is an even shorter lifetime of $(S_1S_0)_{SOL}$ in both cases.

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COMMUNICATION

By introducing dibenzodiazahexacene moieties in a dimeric architecture, a new type of SF material was obtained. Solvent dependent triplet quantum yields of up to 125% were achieved.

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